

Evaluation of root canal configuration of permanent mandibular first molar in a Northwestern Maharashtra subpopulation by using CBCT: A Retrospective Cross-sectional Study

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ABSTRACT:

Objective: To assess number of roots and anatomy of root canal of permanent mandibular first molars in Northwestern Maharashtra. **Study design:** 200 CBCT images of patients with permanent mandibular first molars were assessed for canal morphology using Vertucci's classification, including number of roots and canal's anatomy, involving the number and type. The Chi square test was used for statistical analysis. **Results:** The findings revealed that 86% had two roots, while 14% exhibited three roots, with the third root located distolingually. The distribution of canal numbers showed that two canals were present in 1.5%, three canals in 55.5% and four canals in 43%. In mesial roots, Type IV canal was most common at (55%), then Type II (40%), Type VIII (3%), Type I (2%). For distal roots, Type I was most prevalent at (52%), then Type II at (33%), Type V (8%), Type IV (5%), Type III (2%). Notably, all additional roots displayed Type I canal configuration. **Conclusion:** Three canals were typical of two-roots mandibular first molars, with Type I canal in distal roots and Type IV canals in mesial roots. The extra root had Type I configuration.

Keywords: mandibular first molar, Northwestern Maharashtra's population, Vertucci's classification

INTRODUCTION:

Endodontic treatment aims to prevent or to relieve apical periodontitis by proper cleaning, shaping and disinfection that allows for three dimensional obturation.^{1,2} However, main objective for such therapy is frequently compromised due to complexity of root canal anatomy.^{3,4} Therefore, a proper understanding of both normal and variable canal anatomy is necessary for clinical success.⁵ Mandibular first molars are more susceptible to decay and frequently undergo root canal treatment.⁶

Vertucci has categorized anomalies of root canal of permanent teeth into eight different types.⁷ As a result, dentists need to be aware of potential structural deviations.

Root canal anatomy and morphology may vary according to different geographical region and race.^{8,9} Owing to the limited availability of micro-CT, CBCT has recently been proved to be effective in removing

the superimposition of anatomic components and in delivering precise three-dimensional anatomic details.¹⁰

As there is very little literature. So, the current study was designed to evaluate the number of roots and root canal configuration in mesial, distal root of permanent mandibular first molar according to Vertucci's classification in a Northwestern Maharashtra subpopulation by using CBCT.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Oral Medicine and Radiology from June 2024 to September 2024. The 1975 Helsinki Declaration (revised in 2000) obtained ethical clearance from the institutional board (MGV/KBHDC/IEC/18/24).

Sample size:

Formula for calculating sample size (n): $n = Z^2 P(1-P)/d^2$

CBCT images of patients with minimal edentulous area and those with a full mandibular arch were selected from data available on the CBCT unit server. The CBCT scans selected were of patients such as those referred for diagnostic assessments of the mandibular arch. The scans specifically included mandibular first molars.

The inclusion criteria comprised high quality CBCT scans of healthy sound and fully matured mandibular first molars. The exclusion criteria excluded the scans with intraradicular fillings or any type of fixed prosthesis, scans of post coronal and cervical restorations, scans of root resorptions, periapical lesions, calcifications, open apices and fractures, CBCT scans having artefacts or poor resolution.

The ORTHOPHOS XG 3D with Cephalometric attachment (SIRONA, Germany) with an 8cm x 8cm field of view was used to gather 3D X-ray data. Software called SIDEXIS Version 19.4497.23802(ID7) was used to visualize the data.

200 CBCT Scans were retrospectively examined in this study. CBCT scans of the permanent mandibular first molars were evaluated based on following criteria:

- Root canal morphology including number of roots.
- Anatomy of root canal system including type of canals based on Vertucci's classification.

All images were processed using DICOM (Digital IMAGING and Communications in Medicine)-compatible 3D visualization software.

Vertucci *et al.* (1974)¹¹ classified root canal morphology into eight types as shown in Figure 1 and are described as follows: -

Type I: Single canal extends from pulp chamber to apex (1).

Type II: Two separate canals leave pulp chamber and join short of apex to form one canal (2-1).

Type III: One canal leaves the pulp chamber and divides into two in the root; the two then merge to exit as one canal (1-2-1).

Type IV: Two separate canals extend from pulp chamber to apex (2).

Type V: One canal leaves the pulp chamber and divides short of apex into two separate distinct canals with separate apical foramina (1-2).

Type VI: Two separate canals leave the pulp chamber, merge in the body of the root, and redivide short of the apex to exit as two distinct canals (2-1-2).

Type VII: One canal leaves the pulp chamber, divides and then rejoins in the body of the root, and finally redivides into two distinct canals short of apex (1-2-1-2).

Type VIII: Three separate distinct canals extend from pulp chamber to the apex.

Figure 1: Classification of Vertucci's root canal configuration (Vertucci et al. 1974).¹¹

As illustrated in Figure 2, the toolbar was continually moved from floor of pulp chamber to apex to evaluate scans in different planes at 1-mm interval.

Figure 2: Cone beam computed tomography of permanent mandibular first molar in all the three planes.

Statistical Analysis:

The analysis was done for number of roots, root canals, and root canal configuration of permanent mandibular first molar according to Vertucci's classification. Data entries were done in Microsoft Office Excel 2010 and analyses was done using Statistical product and service solution (SPSS) version 22 software. Descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentage were calculated for quantitative variables. The p value was fixed at 0.05. Chi square test was used for comparison of categorical/nominal data.

RESULTS:

Number of roots:

The most prevalent morphology among the 200 permanent mandibular first molars examined was two roots, which were present in 86% of the scans (172 of 200), followed by three roots, which were present in 14% of the scans (28 of 200) as shown in Table 1 with Chi square test value=17.43 and $P < 0.001$ which were statistically significant. Especially the lingual portion of the distal roots had the third root.

Table 1: Prevalence of the number of roots in 200 permanent mandibular first molars

Number of roots	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
One rooted	-	-
Two rooted	172	86%
Three rooted	28	14%
Total	200	100

Number of root canals and canal configuration:

Two, three, and four canals were found in 1.5%, 55.5%, and 43% out of 200, two- and three-rooted permanent mandibular first molars that were examined as shown in Table 2 with $p < 0.05$ which shows significant difference.

Table 2: Prevalence of the number of root canals in permanent mandibular first molars

Number of root canal	Frequency(n)	Percentage (%)
One canals	0	0%
Two canals	3	1.5%
Three canals	111	55.5%
Four canals	86	43%
Total	200	100%

Vertucci's categorization for permanent mandibular first molars were used to classify the canal configurations. The most prevalent pattern in the mesial roots of 200 permanent mandibular molars was Type IV (55%) (110 of 200), which was followed by Type II (40%) (80 of 200), Type VIII (3%), (6 of 200), and Type I (2%), (4 of 200). The most prevalent pattern in the distal roots was Type I (52%) (104 of 200), which was followed by Type II (33%) (66 of 200), Type V (8%) (16 of 200), Type IV (5%) (10 of 200), and Type III (2%) (4 of 200) as shown in Table 3 with $p < 0.05$ which shows significant difference and $p < 0.001$ shows highly significant difference.

Table 3: Root canal configuration for mesial and distal roots of 200 permanent mandibular first molars according to Vertucci's classification.

Root canal configuration	Mesial (n=200) N (%)	Distal (n=200) N (%)	Extra root (n=28) N (%)
Type I	4(2%)	104(52%)	28(100%)
Type II	80(40%)	66(33%)	0(0%)
Type III	0(0%)	4(2%)	0(0%)
Type IV	110(55%)	10(5%)	0(0%)
Type V	0(0%)	16(8%)	0(0%)
Type VIII	6(3%)	0(0%)	0(0%)
Total	200	200	28
P value	P=0.021	P=0.019	P<0.001

The CBCT sections of variations exhibited by scan specimen are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Illustrative cone-beam computed tomography images showcasing the different anatomical variations observed in permanent mandibular first molars within the studied population, categorized according to Vertucci's classification system (A) Mesial root with Type I, II, IV, VIII (B) Distal root with Type I, II, III, IV, V (C) Radix Entomolaris with Type I canal configuration.

DISCUSSION:

From the available literature there is a wide variation related to root anatomy and canal configuration of permanent mandibular first molar in Northwestern Maharashtra subpopulation.¹

The most popular techniques for examining root canal morphology are tooth clearing, canal staining, traditional radiographs, digital radiographs and microcomputed tomographic techniques.¹² Due to limited availability next best tool for evaluation is CBCT. When compared to standard CT scans, CBCT scans provide a number of benefits for dental imaging,

chief among them being the ability to provide detailed resolution 3D images with less radiation exposure and faster scanning timeframes.¹³ CBCT are considered more economical than traditional CT scans.

In this study, 86% (172 of 200) and 14% (28 of 200) of the scans showed two and three roots, respectively. Further, in these scans, three canals 55.5% (111 of 200) had the most common canal configuration followed by four canals 43% (86 of 200) and two canals 1.5% (3 of 200). This result is in accordance with the Atram J *et al.*¹ of an Indian population and Mashyakhy M *et al.*² in a Saudi population.

The prevalent configuration in mesial root was Type IV (55%), which was followed by Type II (40%), Type VIII (3%), and Type I (2%). Additionally, it was observed that canal configuration in mesial root was type IV while distal was type I same was observed in Saudi population.² This finding was in accordance with Zhang R *et al.* in Chinese individuals.⁶ However, this findings differed from Yemini population reported by Senan *et al.* in which type II was common in mesial canal followed by type IV.¹⁴ At apex, the middle mesial canal either joined the mesiobuccal or mesiolingual canals or existing as three different canals. This finding aligns with results of Yang Y *et al.*¹⁵ In a study by Chourasia HR *et al.*⁹ none of the samples of the mesial roots exhibited three different canals at apex.

While in distal root, Type I (52%) was most prevalent, which was followed by Type II (33%), Type V (8%), Type IV (5%), and Type III (2%). In contrast, 72.8% of the distal roots exhibited a type I configuration in the Belgian population, while 78.8% showed a type I configuration in the Chilean population.¹⁶ This finding aligns with results of Palestinian population where type I was prevalent followed by type II, type III.¹⁷ Type II and Type IV were reported higher in Turkish¹⁸, Saudi Arabian¹⁹ and Sudanese population²⁰ in comparison to current study. While root canals with Type III and Type V anatomical configurations in the distal roots are more challenging to navigate and prepare.

In this study, 43% of the studied mandibular first molars had four canals. In order to increase canal identification, the traditional triangle access cavity preparation should be expanded toward the distolingual direction into rectangle form due to the high percentage of two distal canals.

Mandibular first permanent molars usually have two roots located mesially and distally, but in certain group of population an additional root is usually distolingually situated known as radix entomolaris (RE),²¹ an anatomical variation in human mandibular molars, specifically seen in the first molar considered as a normal morphologic variant which contributed to 14% of the population with a type I canal configuration which was higher than that of previous reported studies on Indian population which were 5.3%,⁹ 4.55%,²² 4.67%,²³ while it was lower than studies on Taiwanese (25.3%)²⁴, Korean (24.5%)²⁵ and Eskimos (21.7%)²⁶ populations.

Despite the limitations inherent in its design and scope, this retrospective study, which includes 200 CBCT scans, adds significant insights to the field. Additional research should have a multicentric approach, be prospective, have a big sample size, and include a range of ethnic groups in order to get more thorough results.

Clinical Implications:

The findings demonstrate the anatomical differences between mandibular first molars in Northwestern Maharashtra, highlighting the significance of comprehending root canal configurations for successful endodontic treatment, guaranteeing favourable results, and reducing root canal therapy complications in diverse populations.

CONCLUSION:

The most frequent morphology of Northwestern Maharashtra subpopulation's permanent mandibular first molars were two-rooted teeth with three canals (two mesial and one distal). Type IV (55%) in mesial roots and Type I (52%) in distal roots were most common configurations seen. In teeth with three roots, the extra root was situated distolingually in 14% of the scans examined and displayed type I root canal configuration.

Conflict of Interest:

There are no conflicts of interest.

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